

EVALUATION OF STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOR OF LNG INSULATION SYSTEM UNDER IMPACT LOADS

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Keywords: LNG carrier insulation system, Mark III, Sloshing, Dry drop test, Impact performance.

1 Introduction

In recent, a number of vast sizes of the LNG carrier (LNGC) are fabricated in industrial fields, and the size of the insulation system (IS) is rapidly increased [1]. The huge size of IS can be encountered the severe loads such as sloshing loads, impulsive loads, etc. In order to ensure the structural integrity of LNGC IS, it is necessary to investigate the structural behavior under arbitrary loads [2].

The structural behavior with respect to the impact loads is previously studied by authors, for instance, Chun et al. [2,3] and Lee et al. [4] have studied the failure characteristics of structural members of IS such as the fiber reinforced polyurethane foam (RPUF). In their studies, the failure of IS under impact loads was observed between mastic and lower RPUF. Moreover, the amount of the recovery and permanent deformation is analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. The detail failure phenomenon is investigated using the fiber optic sensors. In these contexts, the proportional relationship between failure amount and permanent deformation is analyzed.

In the other hand, in order to reduce the permanent deformation of IS, the aluminum-fiber combined vibration isolated layer (VIL) is implemented into the IS. Although there are lots of application of VIL during the fabrication of IS in industrial fields, the structural behavior have not been investigated yet. Hence, in the present study, the structural behavior of the VIL embedded IS (VIL IS) under impact loads is investigated. A series of the impact test for VIL IS are carried out with respect to various drop weights and heights. The recovery/permanent deformation and reaction force are specifically observed. Moreover, the obtained results are

compared with the without VIL IS experimental results.

2 Experimental Apparatus

Fig. 1 shows the schematic of test specimen of MARK-III IS. The dimension is 500 mm × 500 mm × 270 mm (length × breadth × depth). The VIL is implemented into the upper side of plywood. The dry drop weight is collided into the VIL side.

Fig. 1 Dry drop test specimen of MARK-III VIL IS

Fig. 2 Photograph of dry drop test facility

Table 1 Scenarios of dry drop test

No	Weight (kgf)	Height (m)	Thickness of damper (VIL)
1	260 kgf	0.5	-
2			2.5 mm
3		1.0 m	-
4			2.5 mm
5		1.5 m	-
6			2.5 mm
7		2.0 m	-
8			2.5 mm
9		2.5 m	-
10			3.0 mm
11			6.0 mm
12			9.0 mm
13		3.0 m	-
14			3.0 mm
15			6.0 mm
16			9.0 mm
17		3.0 m (pressurized)	-
18			3.0 mm
19			6.0 mm
20			9.0 mm
21	680 kgf	0.5 m	-
22			3.0 mm
23			6.0 mm
24			9.0 mm
25		1.0 m	-
26			3.0 mm
27			6.0 mm
28			9.0 mm

Fig. 2 shows the photograph of the dry drop test facility for MARK-III VIL IS. The dry drop weight and height are 3 m and 260/680 kgf, respectively. In order to obtain the various impact energies, the air pressure device is implemented. The original dry drop speed is 6.0 m/s and the additional speed using air pressure device is 8.5 m/s.

Table 1 shows the test scenarios of the present study. The drop times of Test No. 1-20 and Test No. 21-28 are single and 10 times (cyclic), respectively. In order to investigate the structural behavior under cyclic impact loads, the 10 times of dry drop test are carried out.

Fig. 3 shows the custom-built-type reaction force-displacement measurement system. The relationship between reaction force and time can be obtained by the load sensors and the dynamic strain logger. In addition, the relationship between displacement and time can be acquired by the high speed/quality camera and track eye motion analysis (TEMA) program. In the present study, the deformation was captured 1,000 figures per second. The deformation can be specifically measured by tracking the reference point on the IS using TEMA program.

Fig. 3 Photograph of custom-built-type reaction force-displacement measurement system

3. Results and Discussions

Fig. 4 shows the representative relationship between reaction force and time when the drop weight and height are 680 kgf and 0.5 m, respectively. Fig. 5 shows the representative relationship between deformation and time during the drop weight and height are 680 kgf and 0.5 m, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 4, two kinds of peak reaction force were observed at 4 ms and 8 ms. At this moment, the maximum pressure was 10-32 bar. According to the related previous studies such as Bass et al. [5], the conservative sloshing pressure of LNGC IS is 24.5 bar. Therefore, it is confirmed that the experimental results of the present study are reasonable.

In addition, the first peak of the reaction force of the VIL IS is less than the without VIL IS. However, in the second peak of the reaction force, the amount is same each other. It is considered that the first reaction force is reduced because of the damping effect of VIL. Nevertheless, the second reaction force is not related to the VIL. Hence, using the VIL, a certain level of reaction force can be prevented, and the slight impact damage due to the impact/sloshing force can be reduced. As shown in Fig. 5, the maximum deformation was observed at 8-10 ms, and the recovery/permanent deformations were also measured after 8-10 ms. The maximum and permanent deformations of the VIL IS is less than the without VIL IS. Hence, it is confirm that the VIL can considerably diminish the deformation induced by impact loads.

Fig. 4 Relationship between reaction force and time at weight 680 kgf, height 0.5 m drop test

Fig. 5 Relationship between deformation and time at weight 680 kgf, height 0.5 m drop test

Fig. 6 Relationship between maximum displacement and thickness of VIL regarding to cyclic impact loads at weight 680 kgf, height 0.5 m drop test

Fig. 6 shows the relationship between the maximum displacement and the thickness of VIL regarding to the cycles of impact loads. As shown in this figure, as the cycles are increased, the maximum displacement was increased. Moreover, as the thickness of VIL is increased, the maximum displacement was decreased. According to the cyclic drop test, it is considered that the VIL IS became crushed as the impact loads are repeated, and the maximum displacement is quite sensitive to the

thickness of VIL. Hence, it is important to design the adequate thickness of VIL in order to ensure the robust IS under impact/sloshing loads.

The experimental results are summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2 Experimental results of test scenario No. 1-8

Weight (kgf)	Height (m)	Maximum force (kN)		Maximum displ.(mm)	
		0	2.5	0	2.5
260	0.5	270	263	1.9	1.9
	1.0	406	392	3.5	2.9
	1.5	513	463	7.4	5.7
	2.0	579	577	8.2	8.3

Table 3 Experimental results of test scenario No. 9-28

Weight (kgf)	Height (m)	Maximum force (kN)				Maximum displ.(mm)			
		0	3	6	9	0	3	6	9
260	2.5	650	665	660	621	7.9	7.8	7.1	6.9
	3.0	728	732	722	698	9.5	8.4	8.0	8.4
	C	815	758	782	771	11.4	10.2	9.5	8.3
Weight (kgf)	Height (m)	Maximum force (kN)				Maximum displ.(mm)			
		0	3	6	9	0	3	6	9
680	0.5	520	487	458	458	5.5	3.8	4.6	3.8
	1.0	833	803	775	667	7.6	7.1	7.7	6.1

Acknowledgment

This research was supported by the Basic Science Research Program through the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF), funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (2011-0003879). The authors are pleased to acknowledge the support of Samsung Heavy Industries, Co., Ltd.

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